

The Effect of Part-time Employment on Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development in Plateau State.

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Abstract

Part time employment is an integral part of employment practice in the labor market of all countries. These categories of workers have been employed by Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (MSMEs) and they perform significant roles in economic growth and development of MSMEs and national economies. The Nigerian government had an unfavorable perception of part time employment such that in the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP), there was planned reduction in part time employment that was not achieved. In the National Development Plan (NDP) and the Agenda 2050, the focus is on full time employment without any attention on part time employment. This study sets out to find out if these categories of workers contribute to the development of MSMEs despite the negative perception of the government. Discrete choice models were used and it was found that they contributed to the reduction of being a micro business enterprise and contributed to the probability of remaining a small and medium scale business. In terms of hours spent at work, it was found that there is a higher probability of remaining in the small and medium scale category with more hours (greater than 2 hours) of work. It was therefore recommended that minimum hours be fixed for part time employment among MSMEs.

Keywords: Micro, Small and Medium scale enterprises, Part-time employment, Development, Logit.

1.0: INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMEs) have been major agents of economic growth, development and inclusiveness in national development. They are providers of employment and they make substantial contributions to the gross domestic product of countries. Due to labor laws and cost of fulltime employment, employers of labor give preference to part-time employment and employees prefer part-time employment for various reasons. The Bureau of Labor Statistics (2025) stated that, in the United States of America (USA), as at February 2025, about 4.9 and 3.2 million persons were part-time workers due to economic reasons and slack work or business conditions respectively. About 22.4 million were in such employment because of noneconomic reasons and 1.2 million were part-time workers because they could find only part-time jobs.

According to Garner, Kampelmann and Rycx (2013) in the last three decades, part time employment had become the major feature of many structural markets in Europe and North America. The International Labour Organization[ILO] (2017) stated that young people have multiple jobs that are non-standard in nature, which implies that they have little prospects of remaining in a particular employment for a lifetime. In like France, Italy, Poland, South Africa, Turkey and, marginally, Greece there had been an increase in temporary workers. Between 1995 and 2005 over 40 million jobs had been created due to the expansion of international trade but job creation has gone hand in hand with the proliferation of non-standard work contracts in developed economies – temporary work, part-time employment – and a persistently large informal economy in developing countries (International Labour Organization[ILO] and World Trade Organization[WTO], 2009). This position was further buttressed by Hamandia-Güldenber (2004) and Rubery, Bi-Swinglehurst and Rafferty (2024) that the number of part time workers as a proportion of total employment in most industrialized countries had increased over the last 20 years with Netherlands having the highest number of part-time workers who are nearly one-third of all workers. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2025), labor situation showed that over 31 million part-time workers were employed in all industries in the United States of America (USA). In the United Kingdom (UK), 24 percent of all employees while in Nigeria, part time employees had been above 14 percent (Bako, Muthoga, & Maingi, 2023).

There is no universal definition of what constitutes part-time work except that those in this category, work fewer hours compared to those who are considered full time. Those who work for 30 hours are classified as part time employees in Finland, Canada and New Zealand while those that work for 37 hours in the Netherlands are considered part-time workers. In Hungary and turkey it is 36 hours while in japan, the United States of America and Sweden, 35 hours of work is considered part-time (Hamandia-Güldenber, 2004). In Nigeria, full time employment is considered as employment that is for at least 8 hours a day or 40 hours' work week while those who work for less these hours are considered part time employees. The operational hours of most MSMEs in Nigeria showed that the employment structure of these categories of businesses were largely part time. According to Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria [SMEDAN] (2021) was less than the minimum 8 hours a day as 67.1 percent operate for 4 hours or less and 30.5 operate for between 5 and 8 hours a day. Despite this, the government had not been favorably disposed to promoting part time work. The Economic Growth and Recovery Plan (EGRP) of 2017-2020, targeted a part-time employment reduction rate of 2.61 percent between 2016 and 2017 (17.19 percent in 2017 from 19.8 percent in 2016) but instead, it increased to 20.8 percent in 2017. In 2018, the targeted rate was 17.3 percent (a reduction of 0.11 percent) but instead, it increased to 20.1 percent. The 2020 target is 15.69 percent but 28.16 percent was the realized rate as of the second quarter of 2020. Part-time employment had been above 14 percent between 2010 and 2018. In the national Development Plan (NDP) 2021 to 2025 and Agenda 2050, the plans targeted 21 and 165 million full time jobs to be created by 2025 and 2050 respectively, without any mention of part time employment (Bako, Muthoga, & Maingi, 2023; Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning, 2021).

Over the years sustained economic growth had been problematic, due to various factors. This challenge had resulted in dissatisfaction among citizens with unrest in some countries because of associated high cost of living. MSMEs have a fundamental role to play in order to reverse the growth slowdown and facilitate inclusivity. This is usually done through the employment of part-time workers which impacts the output, growth and development of such businesses. Among member countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) MSMEs (businesses that employ less than 250 persons), provide employment for about 65 percent employment, and contribute about 53 percent of national value added in the business sector in 2019. In the same year, among G20 economies, 66

percent of employment was by small units (those with less than 50 employees) and they are the main source of employment Worldwide (International Labour Organization [ILO] and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2021). MSMEs have been playing vital roles in the development of Nigeria and, have contributed to economic growth in all sectors. The nation as at 2020 had 39,654,385 MSMEs, made up of 96.9 percent micro enterprises and 3.1 percent small and medium scale businesses. About 61,954,073 persons were engaged by MSMEs out of which 16,042,067 employments were generated by the informal sub-sector. This was an increase of 3.7 percent of the sector's contribution to employment in the country. Agricultural, manufacturing, other services, wholesale and retail sectors had the highest number of MSMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria[SMEDAN], 2021).

Nano and Micro business in Nigeria are those that employ a maximum of 2 and, 3-9 employees. They also have a turnover of less than 3 million and between 3 and 25 million respectively. Small and medium scale enterprises are those who employ 10 to 49 and 50 to 199 employees and a turnover of 25 to less than 100 million and 100 million and less than 1 billion naira respectively (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria[SMEDAN], 2021). An improvement in the output of firms and eventually, higher employment of workers will determine the status of such a firm. The cost of hiring full time workers may be quite high and prohibitive for most MSMEs which will make the employment of part-time workers quite attractive. There is also the changing nature of work through the effect of technology especially with the advent of COVID-19. The need to take care of the family and to free time for the pursuit of other interest are some of the factors that have contributed to the growth and popularity of part-time employment.

MSMEs in Nigeria, despite their importance had not performed well because of several factors that include poor managerial skills, inadequate understanding of the business, low level of education and employment of relatives (Dada & Salisu, 2008). To mitigate these, especially the inadequacy of skilled workers as full time employees that adversely affects effective growth and development of MSMEs and their ability to provide employment and contribute to national economic growth, MSMEs tend to utilize part-time workers. The increase in national minimum wage in 2024 has added to the cost of hiring full time labor. This will also make MSMEs rely more on part-time employment as coping mechanism. Moreover the desire not to lose skilled manpower also makes part time employment attractive

to MSMEs. Part-time employment enables them to hire skilled manpower for a short period of time especially in seasons of high demand because of the ease of scheduling such category of workers. Large companies are able to attract and retain highly skilled workers compared to MSMEs because they are able to pay higher and lucrative wages. This then begs the question; does part-time employment contribute to the growth and development of MSMEs in Nigeria? What is the effect of such employees on MSMEs in the country? These are pertinent questions because the medium term national development plan targets a diversified economic base anchored on robust MSMEs, an economic growth rate that will take 10 million people out of poverty between 2021 and 2025, and increase employment generation by 25 million which consists of 10 million from direct inputs and 15 million from skills acquisitions and other interventions (Federal Ministry of Budget and National Planning, 2021).

Various studies have been undertaken on MSME business, part-time employment and labor productivity (Bako, Muthoga, & Maingi, 2023; Rubery, Bi-Swinglehurst, & Rafferty, 2024; Garnero, Kampelmann, & Rycx, 2013), MSME financing (Pauka, 2015) without particular focus on part time employment and how it affects these categories of businesses. The objective of this study is to determine the effect of part-time employment on MSMEs in Plateau State Nigeria, which will also extend the literature in this direction. The hours with the highest number of employees effect on part time will also be analyzed. This study is divided into four sections. Section one of is on the introduction and background of study, theoretical and empirical literature review is discussed in section 2. Sections three and four consist of the methodology and discussion of findings and section five concludes the study with policy recommendations.

2.0: THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW.

Human capital theory according to Fix (2018) originated with the work of Mincer (1958), Schultz (1961) and Becker (1962). The theory posit that improvement in human capital leads to higher productivity and eventually higher income. The portion of this theory related to human capital and productivity is relevant to this study. Part-time employees have acquired various skills that is expected to contribute to the development of various MSMEs that they work for by boosting productivity thus leading to the growth of the firm from micro to small, medium and eventually large scale firm.

Garnero, Kampelmann and Rycx (2013) Studied part-time employment effects on the productivity of firms in Belgium and found that part-time employees generate employer rents and further interaction between gender and part-time employment revealed that positive part-time productivity effect was driven by male part-time workers, working for more than 25 hours. Bako, Muthoga and Maingi (2023) studied eight sectors of the Nigerian economy using panel data random effect model. The study found that part time employment had a positive and statistically significant effect on labor productivity in the country. Devicienti, Grinza and Vennoni (2018) found that in Italy an increase in the share of part timers was associated with a 1.45 percent reduction in productivity. This finding was due to horizontal rather than vertical part time arrangement and firms that accommodate workers request by the use of part timers suffer the most. Pauka (2015) Studied firm performance and innovation with regards to part-time employment in Germany. Part-time employment was found to have adverse impact on firm financial performance. Those with the fewest number of working hours had the most adverse impact. This negative impact was not found on innovation, and there was no significant difference between part and full time workers impact on innovation.

3.0: METHODOLOGY.

3.1: STUDY AREA

The study was carried out within Plateau State in the North Central Region of Nigeria. The State consists of 17 local government councils within the Federal structure of the country. According to SMEDAN (2021), in the year 2020, the state had about 32,028 MSMEs while those with formal registration at the corporate affairs commission were 14,558 MSMEs in the state.

3.2: DATA COLLECTION AND DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS.

Data was collected based on random sampling of two local governments each in two senatorial zones (Central and Southern). Due to the size of the Northern zone, three local governments were sampled. Firms were classified as Nano and micro, small and medium scale enterprises based on the number of employees as defined in the MSMEs survey 2021. The Nano category was classified alongside the micro business category. A total of 268 employees were sampled out of which 126 were those who worked for less than eight hours a day (part time workers). Those who worked for less than two hours were 23.81 percent while those that work for two and three hours were the least at 1.59 and 5.56 percent respectively.

Furthermore 11.11 and 9.52 percent work for four and five hours respectively. Employees that work for six and seven hours were 24.60 and 23.81 percent respectively. They constitute the highest number of part time employees at 31 and 30 persons.

3.3: MODEL SPECIFICATION.

The classification of MSMEs according to the number of employees meant that there is order. Those with fewer employees were ranked lower than those with a greater number of employees. Because of this and the primary nature of data collected, the study employed logistic regression model, which is specified thus

$$Y_i^* = X_i' \beta + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where Y_i^* is an ordered dependent variable with the following codes: 1=Micro, 2=Small, 3=Medium scale businesses respectively. X_i' is a vector of explanatory variables that consists of Hours of work, locations, age of firm, β is a vector of parameters and ε_i is the stochastic term. Equation 1 is specified as follows

$$Y_i^* = \beta_1 hrt_i + \beta_2 loc_i + \beta_3 agf_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Where Y_i^* is as defined in equation 1, hrt_i is number of hours of work (those with less than 8 hours a day), loc_i is location, agf_i is age of firm and ε_i is the error term.

4.0: PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

Tables 3.1 and 3.2 shows the result of part time employment and peak hours of part time employment on MSMEs in Plateau State.

Table 3.1. Part-time employment effect on MSMEs

Variables	Average Marginal Effect	Delta standard error	method	P-value
Hours of work				

Micro	-0.036	0.015	0.018**
Small	0.029	0.012	0.019**
Medium	0.006	0.004	0.094*
Location			
Micro	-0.087	0.020	0.000***
Small	0.072	0.017	0.000***
Medium	0.015	0.007	0.040**
Age of firm			
Micro	-0.011	0.005	0.034**
Small	0.009	0.004	0.039**
Medium	0.002	0.001	0.092*

Note: *, **, *** signifies statistical significance at 10, 5 and 1 percent respectively.

Source: Authors Computation Using STATA 15.

From table 3.1 part time employment was statistically significant at 5 percent and it was found to reduce the probability of remaining in a micro scale firm level by 3.6 percent with an increase in part time work hours by one. This implies that part time workers contribute to the chances of a firm growing from the micro level to a small scale business level. The probability of remaining in the small scale firm category increases by 2.9 percent with an increase in part time employment by one hour. This implies an improvement in the survival of the business and its possibility of growing into the medium scale category. In the medium scale business category, part time employees were found to increase the probability of remaining in this category of business by 0.6 percent and was weakly statistically significant, which is at 10 percent. This finding implied that part time workers contribute positively to the development of these categories of producers. This improvement is traditionally measured through improved output, revenue and number of employees. With regards to firm output, this is similar to the finding of Garnero, Kampelmann and Rycx (2013) among Belgian firms, where part time employees contribute positively to firm rents, and Bako, Muthoga, and Maingi (2023) found positive and statistically significant effect of part time employment on labor productivity in Nigeria. It was contrary to the findings of Devicienti, Grinza and Vennoni (2018) in Italy where part time work had negative impact on firm productivity.

The location of the firm was found to reduce the probability of remaining a micro firm enterprise by 8.7 percent and was statistically significant at one percent. While for small scale firms the probability of remaining in this category of business was found to increase with changes in location by 7.2 percent. In the medium scale category, the chance of remaining was found to be 1.5 percent. Age of firm was also found to reduce the probability of remaining in the micro firm level by 1.1 percent as the firm grows older. In the small scale category, the probability of remaining was 0.9 percent while in the medium scale, it was found that the probability was 0.2 percent and weakly statistically significant.

The result above was further disaggregated to determine if the hours that correspond to the highest number of part time employees as showed by the descriptive statistics, affects these business categories. The result is presented in table 3.2

Table 3.2: Effect of Highest Part-time Employment Hours on MSMEs.

Hours of work	Average Marginal Effects	Delta method error	P-value
Micro			
Less than 2 hours	-0.029	0.009	0.002
Six hours	-0.036	0.016	0.021
Seven hours	-0.037	0.016	0.021
Small			
Less than 2 hours	0.026	0.009	0.004
Six hours	0.029	0.012	0.021
Seven hours	0.028	0.011	0.014
Medium			
Less than 2 hours	0.003	0.001	0.024
Six hours	0.008	0.005	0.127
Seven hours	0.009	0.006	0.153

Note: *,**,*** signifies statistical significance at 10,5 and 1 percent respectively.

Source: Authors Computation Using STATA 15.

From table 3.2 those who work for less than two hours and those that work for six and seven hours respectively, reduce the probability of remaining in the micro firm business category by

2.9, 3.6 and 3.7 percent respectively. This implies that the more the hours put in, the higher the probability of leaving this category of business. Firms have a higher possibility of migrating from the micro level to a higher classification because of the presence and number of hours that these workers put into their jobs.

For the small scale firm level, the probability of remaining in this category of business increases from 0.26 percent to 0.29 as part time hours of work moves from less than two hours to six hours but the probability reduces to 2.8 percent at the seven hours of employment. The medium scale category result shows that the probability increases from 0.3 to 0.8 and 0.9 percent respectively at less than two hours to six and seven hours. At the sixth and seventh hour it becomes statistically insignificant. Thus the lowest success probability is associated with the fewest number of part time working hours. This is because those who work fewer number of hours will have less experience, lower skill sets and less training that will boost their ability to contribute to the growth of the firm at its chances of success. This finding is similar to (Pauka, 2015) in Germany where those with the fewest working part time hours had lowest productivity contribution and highest adverse impact on firm financial performance.

5.0: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

Part-time employment is an integral part of labor market structure and the services rendered by these category of employees is crucial for economic growth and development. Nigeria is determined to ensure rapid economic growth and diversifying the economic base through robust MSME growth and development. MSMEs are cardinal to the development of growth of economies. Part time employment reduced the probability of remaining a micro business enterprise. The more the hours put in the higher the probability of not remaining a micro business and remaining a small and medium scale firm or producer.

The government, through the ministry of labor and employment in conjunction with the Nigeria employers consultative association, should stipulated the minimum number of hours that people will be employed as part time workers. This should not be less than three hours a day.

Micro businesses should be supported by the government and non-governmental organizations with a payroll support fund. It should be targeted at the payment of workers' wages to ensure that they employ more workers operate for more hours and grow to the small

and medium scale categories. This will increase the employment of more workers and facilitate economic growth.

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